

Bivalent Metal-Chelates of *p*-Aminobenzoylglycine**

SRIKUMAR MUKERJEE and NARENDRA S. RAWAT*

Chemical Laboratories, Indian School of Mines, Dhanbad-826004. (Bihar) India.

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pH metric studies of the complexes of *p*-aminobenzoylglycine (PABG) with Cu(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) were carried out by Bjerrum's *pH*-titration technique at 27°, and constant ionic strength of 0.1M sodium-perchlorate. The overall proton-ligand stability constant (log *pH*) and the metal-ligand formation constants were calculated by Irving and Rossotti technique. Irving and William's order is followed in case of all metal ions, except in the case of Cd(II) and Co(II).

AMINO acids which form stable complexes have analytical importance in separation of transition metals and rare earths¹. A study of these complexes is also important in biological chemistry, in that the accumulation of sufficient data on amino acid complexes with metal ions may contribute to a better understanding of the types of linkages involved in metal-protein interactions. The role of *p*-aminobenzoylglycine (PABG) in the metabolism of living bodies was investigated by different workers²⁻⁴. A survey of the literature shows, that apart from its bio-chemical properties, no systematic work has been done, with regard to its complexing tendency, and hence the present investigation was undertaken. The present study reveals the formation of some metal complexes of bivalent ions like Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ with the ligand PABG. The parameters have been calculated by Calvin-Bjerrum's titration technique^{5,6} as modified by Irving & Rossotti⁷. The protonation constants of the ligand are also determined.

Experimental

Solutions of *p*-Aminobenzoylglycine (Fluka), nitrate salt of copper, nickel cadmium, cobalt and chloride salt of manganese and zinc were all prepared, by dissolving accurately weighed amounts in double distilled water. All the metal ion reagents were of Analar grade. Solution of carbondioxide free sodiumhydroxide (BDH) and perchloric acid (Riedel) was prepared and standardised potentiometrically. Stock solution of sodium perchlorate was prepared by dissolving Analar sample of NaClO₄·H₂O(Merck) in double distilled water.

pH measurements were done by Philips *pH* meter using a glass-calomel electrode assembly at a constant temperature 27±0.02°, and ionic strength of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate.

Procedure

Solution mixture containing (a) acid (5 ml of 0.03M perchloric acid and 5 ml of 0.1 M sodium perchlorate),

(b) ligand (mixture 'a' and 5 ml of 0.01 M PABG), (c) complex (mixture 'b' and 5 ml of 0.005 M metal solution) were taken, and total volume raised to 50 ml. The mixtures (a), (b), (c) were separately titrated against standard 0.1840 M sodiumhydroxide solution.

Results and Discussion

The respective metal ions with the ligand were titrated against alkali. From the shift in *pH* titration curves (Fig. 1), values of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and P_L were calculated by Irving and Rossotti method⁷. It was noted that the ligand curve B is slightly shifted to the left of the acid titration curve A at lower *pH* values. This indicates gradual neutralization of -COOH group of the zwitter ion, which is complete at a *pH*, where the curve B crosses the curve A. The onward course followed by the curve B to the right of A may subsequently be concluded as owing to the neutralization of second proton from the ligand, which occurs due to the protonation of carbonyl group by the rearrangement

Gillespie⁸ *et al.* have proved such a rearrangement by NMR studies. Such a rearrangement has also been observed in the case of complex formation, which occurs due to the shift in the metal titration curves with the ligand titration curve, indicating the liberation of protons. It appears that the amino group at the para position does not take part in chelation in an aqueous medium.

Thus only two protonation constant values are expected (below 10.5 *pH*) upto a certain range of *pH* value. Fig. 2 shows the formation curve of the proton-ligand system, the log K_1^H value for PABG

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* For correspondence.

TITRATION CURVES, METAL-PABG SYSTEM
($\mu = 0.1\text{ M}$)

Fig 1.

being 9.89 at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$ and $\log K_2^H$ being 4.29 at $\bar{n}_A=1.5$ respectively. The values were also calculated at different pH by interpolation at various $\bar{n}_A$ value method, which gave the value of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ as 9.30 and 4.37 respectively. The values obtained by different methods are fairly in good agreement.

PROTON LIGAND FORMATION CURVE OF PABG SYSTEM
($\mu = 0.1\text{ M}$)

Fig. 2.

In case of Cu, Co, Cd and Zn, the titration curves of the solutions (b) and (c) almost coincides at higher pH value (~ 11.2), and in case of Ni and Mn, titration curves of solution (c) intersect the titration curve of solution (b) at pH values 10.75 and 10.80 respectively. The coincidence of the curves indicate that the reagent is completely ionized, and the metal complexes are not hydrolysed even at higher pH values. Divergence or crossing over of the curves at higher pH value is due to hydrolysis⁹⁻¹².

The plots of $\bar{n}$ and P_L (Fig. 3) show that for Mn(II), $\bar{n}$ attains maximum value of only one, but with other ions, Cu(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) approaches two, thus indicating that with Mn²⁺, only one complex ML is formed, whereas in Cu²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ two complexes ML and ML₂ are formed stepwise.

For ML chelate system of Mn²⁺, the stability constants were calculated by interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ value method. For other systems of ML and ML₂, the $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were calculated by applying interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values, interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ values and mid-point method¹³, which are given in Table 1.

A comparison of the stability constants of these metal complexes show that the sequence of stability is.

FORMATION CURVES OF METAL-PABG SYSTEMS
($\mu = 0.100\text{ M}$)

Fig. 3.

TABLE—1. STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME BIVALENT METAL ION COMPLEXES WITH PABG

Metal ions	Stability constants		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Cu(II)	9.50 *	4.90	14.40
	9.63 **	4.79	14.42
(mean value)	9.56	4.84	14.40
Ni(II)	7.50 *	3.30	10.80
	7.46 **	3.23	10.69
(mean value)	7.47	3.26	10.73
Co(II)	8.41 *	3.50	11.91
	7.69 **	3.44	11.13
(mean value)	8.05	3.47	11.52
Mn(II)	5.49 *	—	5.49
	5.22 **	—	5.22
(mean value)	5.35	—	5.35
Zn(II)	8.60 ***	4.00 *	12.61
	8.80 **	4.31	13.11
(mean value)	8.70	4.15	12.85
Cd(II)	8.80 **	4.75 *	13.55
	8.19 **	4.91	13.10
(mean value)	8.49	4.83	13.32

* Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ value method.** Interpolation at various $\bar{n}$ value method.

*** Mid-point method.

From the sequence, it is observed that Irving-William's natural order^{1,4} $Zn < Cu > Ni > Co > Fe > Mn$ of stability of complexes is obeyed in so far as $Zn < Cu > Ni > Mn$ among bivalent metal ion studied

here. This order is also observed by Mellor & Maley^{1,6} and confirmed by several workers^{6,17}.

The regular variation of these properties reaches a discontinuity in the present case of Cd^{2+} and Co^{2+} . In the case of cadmium which should come between Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} , a considerable deviation from the expected trend has been observed. This is unexpected in the case of hard base ligands. In order to check the validity of such conditions, experiments were performed at several ionic strengths, and in each case it was observed that the stability of Cd^{2+} is greater than Zn^{2+} . In this case, one can say that the forces involved in the complex formation may not be similar to those in the other cases. Here the formation of the complex may be stronger¹⁸ as compared with zinc, cobalt, nickel and manganese. Here the stability of Co^{2+} is greater than Ni^{2+} . This order is observed by a number of workers¹⁹⁻²². This may be attributed to Jahn-Teller stabilisation of $Co(II)$ similar to $Cu(II)$ and to favourable entropy effect, while partial oxidation of the $Co(II)$ complexes is not absolutely ruled out.

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